

Effect of physical parameters on alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase during the production of acetic acid from ethanol by an ethanol resistant strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀

Modhurima Chakraborti*, R. K. Basu and A. K. Banik

Department of Chemical Engineering, Biochemical Division, University of Calcutta,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : modhurima_chakraborty@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 15 December 2008, accepted 5 February 2009

Abstract : An ethanol resistant strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀ was examined to ascertain its acetic acid production. The influence of physical parameters on acetic acid production and activities of alcohol dehydrogenase (alcohol : NAD⁺ oxidoreductase; E.C. 1.1.1.1) and aldehyde dehydrogenase (aldehyde : NAD⁺ (P⁺) oxidoreductase; E.C. 1.2.1.5) were also observed. The optimal conditions finally found were : initial pH = 4.5, incubation temperature = 30 °C, incubation time = 48 h, volume of medium = 85 ml, age of inoculum = 48 h and cell density = 10.25 × 10⁵. These optimal conditions were also optimum for the activities of the two main regulatory enzymes i.e. alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase.

Keywords : Acetic acid, physical parameters, alcohol dehydrogenase, aldehyde dehydrogenase.

Introduction

Acetic acid as an industrial chemical is produced using yeast by the three step fermentation process. The first step is the production of ethanol from a carbohydrate source, such as glucose. The second step is the production of acetaldehyde by oxidation of ethanol and the third step is the oxidation of acetaldehyde to acetic acid¹⁻³.

Two enzymes such as, alcohol dehydrogenase (alcohol : NAD⁺ oxidoreductase; E.C. 1.1.1.1) and aldehyde dehydrogenase (aldehyde : NAD⁺ (P⁺) oxidoreductase; E.C. 1.2.1.5) are responsible for the production of acetic acid from ethanol³⁻⁷.

Cultivation of microorganism require favourable environment, like - appropriate temperature, pH, incubation period, volume of medium, age of inoculum and cell density. These essential factors in optimum amount work together as a building material for the multiplication of microorganism. Thus the main objective of the present work was to investigate the optimum cultural conditions

for the growth of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀ which gave the maximum activity of the two enzymes to give the maximum production of acetic acid from ethanol.

Experimental

(i) *Microorganism used* : *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀, a newly isolated ethanol resistant strain in our laboratory, have been used in these studies⁸.

(ii) *Medium and cultural conditions* : The maintenance media consisted of 1% D-glucose, 0.5% peptone, 0.5% yeast extract and 1% agar agar powder. pH was adjusted to 5.0. Organism was maintained at 30 °C for 48 h. Inoculum was harvested by washing the slant with sterile distilled water, adjusting the cell density to 2.05 × 10⁵ per ml.

The medium for fermentation consisted of 10% D-glucose, 0.1% KH₂PO₄, 0.5% (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05% MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.1% yeast extract. pH was adjusted to 4.5. Both medium were sterilized at 121 °C and 15 lb/inch² pressure for 15 min.

250 ml conical flasks containing the fermentation medium were inoculated with 5 ml of inoculum and incubated at 30 °C for 96 h.

After fermentation, the cell was separated by centrifugation and the supernatant was used for analysis of acetic

acid and the enzyme assay.

(iii) *Alcohol estimation* : % of alcohol was determined by Gas Chromatography with a Pye Unicam Series 104 with a Flame Ionization Detector on a column of Porapak Q using N₂ as carrier gas. The column temperature and detector temperature were 140 °C and 220 °C respectively. 5 µl sample was injected. *N*-Propanol was used as internal standard⁹.

(iv) *Acetic acid estimation* : Concentration of acetic acid was determined by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) with a TPS Spectra System apparatus using a Biorad Aminex HPX-87H column heated to 40 °C and a Refraction Index Detector (Waters 640). The mobile phase was sulphuric acid (0.005 M) flowing at 0.4 ml/ min¹⁰.

(v) *Assay of alcohol dehydrogenase* : 0.1 ml of supernatant was added to the mixture of 15 mM β-NAD⁺, 50 mM sodium pyrophosphate buffer (pH 8.8) and 95% ethanol and incubated for 6 min at 25 °C in a suitably thermostatted spectrophotometer. Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm. Enzyme activity was expressed as mu/ml. One unit of enzyme activity represents the amount of enzyme which can convert 1.0 µmole of ethanol to acetaldehyde per minute at pH 8.8 at 25 °C¹¹.

(vi) *Assay of aldehyde dehydrogenase* : 0.1 ml of supernatant was added to the mixture of 1 (M) tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0), 20 mM β-NAD⁺, 100 mM acetaldehyde solution, 3 (M) KCl and 1 (M) 2-mercaptoethanol and incubated for 5 min at 25 °C in a suitably thermostatted spectrophotometer. Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm. Enzyme activity was expressed as mu/ml. One unit of enzyme activity represents the amount of enzyme which can oxidize 1.0 µmole of acetaldehyde to acetic acid per minute at pH 8.0 at 25 °C in presence of β-NAD⁺, potassium and thiols⁷.

Results

(i) *Effect of different initial pH of the medium on enzyme activity and production of acetic acid by Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀* :

Acetic acid production (g/L)^{12,9,3} and enzyme activity (mu/ml)¹³ is accomplished by a sudden increase in pH. The optimum pH was determined by adjusting the initial pH of the fermentation medium at different values, like - 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, 6.0. Fig. 1 indicates that, the optimal initial pH of the medium for acetic acid production (g/L) and enzyme activity (mu/ml) is 4.5. Lower amount of acid production and enzyme activity was obtained at lower or higher pH.

Fig. 1. Effect of different initial pH on acetic acid production (g/L), cell growth (g/L)¹ and enzyme activity (mu/ml) of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

(ii) *Effect of different incubation temperatures on enzyme activity during the acetic acid production by Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀* :

Fermentation was carried out at different incubation temperatures, like 27, 30, 33 and 37 °C. Fig. 2 indicates that the temperature of 30 °C favors the production of acetic acid (g/L), cell growth (g/L) and enzyme activity

Fig. 2. Effect of different incubation temperatures on acetic acid production (g/L), cell growth (g/L) and enzyme activity (mu/ml) of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

(mu/ml). Lower values obtained at higher temperature due to the evaporation of ethanol.

(iii) *Effect of different incubation periods on enzyme activity and production of acetic acid by Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀* :

After 48 h of incubation at 30 °C and pH 4.5, we analysed % of alcohol produced by our ethanol resistant

strain and it was found to be 4–5%, because above 5–6% ethanol, both acetic acid and enzyme activity decreases^{3,11}.

Then this ethanol was oxidized to acetic acid at different time periods – 18, 24, 36, 48, 56, 58, 60, 68, 72 and 80 h. Fig. 3 indicates that, enzyme activity (mu/ml) and acetic acid production (g/L) was maximum after 48 h and then decreases, because prolonged incubation can further oxidize acetic acid to CO₂ and H₂O by oxygen present in the fermentation medium².

Fig. 3. Effect of different incubation periods on acetic acid production (g/L), cell growth (g/L) and enzyme activity (mu/ml) of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

(iv) *Effect of different volume of medium on enzyme activity during the production of acetic acid by Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀* :

Fermentation was carried out taking different volume of medium, like – 60, 75, 85, 100, 120, 135 and 150 ml. Fig. 4 indicates that 85 ml of medium exhibits maximum acetic acid production (g/L) and enzymatic activities (mu/ml), while lower enzymatic activities and acid production are obtained in higher and lower volume of medium.

(v) *Effect of different age of inoculum on enzyme activity during the production of acetic acid by Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀* :

For the optimization of the effect of age of inoculum on acid production and enzymatic activity, maintaining all other optimized conditions constant, different aged yeast cultures of 18, 24, 36, 48, 60 and 72 h were used for inoculation purpose. Fig. 5 indicates that the 48 h aged culture favors the optimum acetic acid production (g/L) and enzyme activities (mu/ml), while it is lowered at lower and higher age of inoculum.

Fig. 4. Effect of different volume of medium on acetic acid production (g/L), cell growth (g/L) and enzyme activity (mu/ml) of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 5. Effect of different age of inoculum on acetic acid production (g/L), cell growth (g/L) and enzyme activity (mu/ml) of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

(vi) *Effect of different cell density on enzyme activity during the production of acetic acid by Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀* :

For the optimization of cell density, different volumes of inoculum were taken for fermentation, like – 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 ml. Each volume contains a certain amount of cell density. Fig. 6 indicates that 5 ml of inoculum volume with 10.25×10^5 cell density shows maximum enzymatic activities (mu/ml) and acetic acid production (g/L). Lower values were obtained in higher and lower cell density.

Discussion

From our present studies, the following optimum cul-

Fig. 6. Effect of different cell density on acetic acid production (g/L), cell growth (g/L) and enzyme activity (mu/ml) of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

tural conditions were obtained for maximum enzymatic activities by the ethanol resistant strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀ in order to produce maximum acetic acid.

Initial pH of the medium = 4.5, temperature of incubation = 30 °C, volume of medium = 85 ml, period of incubation for acetic acid production = 48 h, age of inoculum = 48 h and cell density = 2.05×10^5 per ml.

Maintaining all these optimum conditions, we have also found that, kinetics of acetic acid production is identical with the enzyme activity. Gradual increase and decrease of enzyme activity influences the acid production in similar manner. Both of these two enzymes show maximum activities at these optimum conditions.

We have also studied that, upto 24 h of incubation the activity of alcohol dehydrogenase is gradually increasing, because upto this time it gets its substrate i.e. ethanol sufficiently. But after that period of time, the activity is decreased because, ethanol is gradually being converted to acetaldehyde, which is the substrate of another enzyme aldehyde dehydrogenase. Activity of aldehyde dehydrogenase was lower initially and gradually increases upto 48 h. At 48 h, its activity was maximum because the amount of acetaldehyde was maximum then. After that time period its activity starts decreasing and acetic acid production also decreases. But its activity is not negli-

gible upto 72 h, whereas, no considerable activity of alcohol dehydrogenase found even after 68 h.

The cell growth was also maximum when the production of acetic acid was maximum i.e. at 48 h of fermentation.

The next phase of our work is to find out suitable nutrients which are necessary to increase the activity of aldehyde dehydrogenase so that the production of acetic acid can also be increased ultimately.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to the Department of Food Processing Industries and Horticulture, Government of West Bengal for their financial assistance.

References

1. M. Cheryan, S. Parekh, M. Shah and K. Witjitra, *Advances in Applied Microbiology*, 1997, 43, 1.
2. M. E. Silva, A. B. Torres Neto, W. B. Silva, F. L. H. Silva and R. Swarnakar, *Brazilian J. Chemical Engineering*, 2007, 24, 163.
3. S. F. Lu, F. L. Lee and H. K. Chen, *J. Applied Microbiology*, 1999, 86, 55.
4. J. A. Delcour, J. M. Caers and P. Dondeyne, *J. Inst. Brew.*, 1982, 88, 384.
5. T. Nosova, K. Jokelainen, P. Kaihovaara, H. Jousimies-Somer, A. Siitonen, R. Heine and M. Salaspuro, *Alcohol & Alcoholism*, 1996, 31, 555.
6. T. Matysiak-Budnik, K. Jokelainen, P. Karkkainen, H. Makisalo, J. Ohisalo and M. Salaspuro, *J. Pathology*, 1996, 178, 464.
7. K. A. Bostian and G. F. Betts, *Biochem. J.*, 1978, 173, 773.
8. P. Saha and A. K. Banik, *Food Sci. Technol.*, 1998, 42, 127.
9. Association of Official Agricultural Chemists, 1950, 'Official and Tentative Methods of Analysis', 6th ed., Washington D.C.
10. C. Castro-Martinez, B. I. Escudero-Abarca, J. Gomez Rodriguez, P. M. Hayward-Jones and M. G. Aguilar-Uscanga, *J. Food Process Engineering*, 2005, 28, 133.
11. J. H. R. Kagi and B. L. Vallee, *J. Biological Chemistry*, 1960, 235, 3188.
12. J. N. Kim, I. S. Choo, Y. J. Wee, J. S. Yun and H. W. Ryu, *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 2005, 121-124, 861.
13. J. Fibla and R. Gonzalez-Duarte, *J. Biochemical and Biophysical Methods*, 1993, 26, 87.